

Satellite observations provide a global picture of global changes in 24-hr rainfall

Andreas Dobler^{a*}, Rasmus E. Benestad^a, Cristian Lussana^a

^a *The Norwegian Meteorological Institute, Henrik Mohns plass 1, Oslo, Norway*

* Corresponding Author: andreas.dobler@met.no

Abstract

Based on our understanding of physics, we expect that climate change will alter the global hydrological cycle as well as incurring global warming. Hence, it is expected that the rainfall patterns also will change. Satellite-borne instruments provide a unique picture of the Earth, and we present an analysis of space-based rainfall measurements which indicate that the global surface area with 24-hr rainfall has declined since 1998. This finding is also seen in state-of-the-art reanalyses, which too rely strongly on satellite observations through data assimilation. However, it is unclear whether this trend is real and physical, or merely due to inhomogeneities in the satellite and assimilated data. Thus, we also analysed simulations from global climate models (GCMs) to check whether they reproduce and project similar trends. GCMs are not influenced by the introduction of new observing systems over time and make computations based on first physical principles. The results show that the GCMs agree on a shrinking area and a poleward shift of precipitation-days in a warming climate, although the magnitude of the shrinking trend is smaller than in the satellite and reanalysis data. Our analysis also underscores the value of combining three different, partly independent sources of information/data to address questions about global change, where satellite observations play a crucial role.

Keywords: hydrological cycle, precipitation, climate change

1. Introduction

The ongoing global warming is expected to change Earth's hydrological cycle and rainfall patterns, and there have been numerous studies on changes in rainfall that have been published in the scientific literature [1]. Most of the observation-based studies have emphasised local and regional change in rainfall where rain gauges were the main data sources. The network of rain gauge measurements however is irregular, ad-hoc and not truly global as it tends to cover land area only and to provide samples in places conveniently accessible to humans. While a rain gauge represents a point measurement, there are also gridded products that provide a more extensive geographical picture over land, albeit mostly interpolated from rain gauge data as well. To get a truly global picture, it is important to include ocean areas which represent about 70% of Earth's surface area. Such data can be provided by satellite-based observations, or alternatively numerical model systems.

The benefit of a complete global coverage of precipitation is the possibility to address new scientific questions related to the global hydrological cycle. For instance, the question on the total amount of water that typically falls on Earth's surface each day. Increased surface temperatures are expected to bring about higher rates of evaporation and, according to the Clausius-Clapeyron relation, an increased water-holding capacity of the atmosphere. This is expected to yield an increase in the total global precipitation amount, supported by the results presented in [2,3]: In [2], Benestad has estimated an increase in the total

precipitation amount (between 50°S and 50°N) from 1122 Gt per day to 1152 Gt per day in the time period 1998 to 2016 based on satellite data. In [3], based on reanalysis data, the estimated global increase was from 1440 Gt to 1510 Gt per day in the time period 1950 to 2020.

Other questions are related to where the water falls and over what fraction of Earth's surface, and whether global warming affects the area, the spatial scales of the precipitation producing phenomena or the frequency of occurrence of different types of phenomena. To these questions, data from satellite-born remote sensing can provide answers, or at least insights, which data sets based on rain gauge observations can not give.

2. Material and methods

The satellite data for our analysis is provided by the Tropical Rainfall Measurement Mission (TRMM) [4], more specifically we use the daily precipitation product '3B42'. The TRMM data was calibrated with rain gauge data over land and has a spatial resolution of 0.25°. It provides near-global coverage over both land and ocean from 50°S to 50°N (77% of Earth's surface area).

Additionally, our analysis included global daily precipitation data from the ERA5 reanalysis [5] for the time period 1940 to 2020, and GCM projections for the time period 1850-2100 from CMIP6 [6] with greenhouse gas emissions based on the SSP5-8.5 scenario [7]. The methods we applied were area-weighted spatial means and temporal averaging of daily rainfall data.

3. Theory and calculation

In a global hydrological cycle in equilibrium, the amount of evaporated water (E) balances with the amount of precipitation (P): $E = - P$. Higher temperatures are expected to increase the rate of evaporation and thus precipitation.

The amount of precipitated water can be expressed as the product between the area receiving precipitation (A) and the mean amount over the region (μ): $P = A \cdot \mu$. Thus, if precipitation is spread over a larger area, then the mean intensity will be lower, whereas if precipitation is limited to a small fraction of Earth's surface, then the mean intensity will be higher. Hence, the mean intensity of precipitation depends both on the rate of evaporation as well as the area on which it falls.

4. Results

Fig. 1 shows the time series of the daily precipitation area, as the fraction of the total area, in the TRMM and ERA5 data between 50°S and 50°N. In the ERA5 data, the area has decreased from 43% to 40% between 1940 and 2020 (and from 43% to 41% globally, not shown). For TRMM, there is also a decrease apparent, from about 25% to 22%, in agreement with the numbers given by Benestad [2]. For the overlapping period of 1998-2017, the two datasets fairly agree on the temporal evolution. However, the TRMM data shows a precipitation area that is about half the size of the one in ERA5. This can be explained by the fact that while ERA5 is based on accumulated forecasts from a model system, the TRMM data is based on snapshots of the globe. Thus, the TRMM data provides a sharper image of the precipitation area and thus a lower fraction.

The ERA5 shows a large drop in the precipitation area during the period 1985 to 1995. The reason for this drop is still unclear but could be related to aerosols or changes in cloud structures, or be an artefact of changes in the assimilated data [3]. This clearly affects the overall trend, but a negative trend can also be seen in the period after the drop.

The annual mean precipitation area (Fig. 1) is equal to the spatial mean of the annual precipitation-day frequency. Figure 2 shows a map of trends in the annual precipitation-day frequency calculated from the ERA5 data for the period 1950 to 2020. There is a decrease in the area between 50°S and 50°N, most evident over the oceans, causing a decrease in the annual mean precipitation area in this region. Conversely, there is an increase in the polar region, starting at about 50°S in the southern hemisphere, and strongest in the Barents region.

Fig.1. Time series of the daily and annual mean precipitation area as a fraction of the total surface area between 50°S and 50°N for the TRMM and ERA5 data.

Fig.2. Trends in precipitation-days per year in the ERA5 data for the period 1950 to 2020. Only trends significant at the 5% level are shown.

Decreases in the annual precipitation-day frequency are also visible in the 30 year period 1991-2020 in the ERA5 data (Fig. 3). In this period, less areas show a statistical significant trend but there are larger trends. Again, the largest increases are apparent in the Barents region.

Fig.3. As Fig.2 but for the period 1991 to 2020 only. Note the different amplitudes.

Fig. 4 shows the time series of daily precipitation area fractions between 50°S and 50°N as simulated by global climate and Earth system models (GCMs) as well as the ERA5 reanalysis. There is a large spread in the amplitude of the simulated area, likely connected to the model resolution, but most models agree on a decrease in the precipitation area for future projections.

Fig.4. Time series of the annual mean precipitation area as a fraction of the total surface area between 50°S and 50°N from ERA5 and CMIP6 GCMs (following SSP5-8.5).

The GCMs are projecting a shift of precipitation-days from the region 50°S to 50°N into more polar regions (Fig. 5), in agreement with ERA5 (Figs. 2 and 3). Especially for the Arctic region and the end of the 21st century, a large increase in the precipitation-day frequency is projected in the GCMs.

Fig.5. Time series of the precipitation-day frequency at single latitudes for the GCM ensemble median for the time period 1850 to 2100. The vertical lines indicate the period 1950 to 2020.

The zonal mean precipitation-day frequencies for ERA5 (Fig. 6) and TRMM (Fig. 7) reveal an agreement of the three data sources on an extension of the subtropical high, a poleward shift of precipitation-days

and a decrease of the precipitation-day frequency around the equator and ITCZ. The decrease in the frequencies between 50°S and 50°N is partly compensated by an increase in the polar regions. However, the surface area in the polar regions is smaller than at lower latitudes (as it scales by the cosine of the latitude) and the loss in the precipitation area is not fully compensated.

Fig.6 As Fig.5 but for the ERA5 data and the period 1950 to 2020. The vertical line indicates the year 1991.

Fig.7. As Fig. 5 but for the TRMM data and the time period 1998 to 2107.

5. Discussion and Conclusions

The total global precipitation mass, the mean intensity and the global surface fraction receiving precipitation each day have profound implications for nature and society. If the fraction of surface area is becoming smaller, then we can expect more widespread droughts and more intense (average) rainfall where it's wet, and hence more floods. The trend towards a diminishing global area of precipitation combined with increased amounts, as shown in recent studies [2,3], is therefore a serious concern when it comes to global warming and there is a need to test the validity of these findings.

We have here tested an approach involving precipitation data from global climate models along with satellite and reanalysis data. The climate models indicate some changes that are consistent with the

satellite and reanalysis data, e.g. an extension of the subtropical high and a reduction of the precipitation area between 50°S and 50°N. Thus, it is likely that these trends are due to changes in the dynamics and thermodynamics within Earth's climate system. However, for some changes, like the drop in the precipitation area in ERA5 between 1985 and 1995, we did not find support in the GCM data and further investigations are needed.

Global precipitation indicators, prevailing the availability of the data, can provide new insights on precipitation patterns. However, such indicators are often neglected, or at least underrepresented, in assessments of Earth's climate, e.g. the WMO's Global Climate Indicators (<https://gcos.wmo.int/en/global-climate-indicators>). Satellite-based datasets, although still relatively short in time to assess robust trends, provide a unique global picture of Earth making it possible to calculate these indicators at daily or even sub-daily scales.

Furthermore, satellite-based observation of trends in vegetation, salinity or groundwater storage may add independent sources of information that may potentially provide indications of the spatial distribution of precipitation [8].

Acknowledgements

We acknowledge the teams at NASA and ECMWF whose efforts have produced the TRMM and ERA5 data, respectively. We also want to thank CMIP and the participating modeling groups as well as the World Climate Research Programme's Working Group on Coupled Modeling responsible for CMIP to make the GCM data available.

References

- [1] IPCC (2022) Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation, and Vulnerability. Contribution of Working Group II to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change [H.-O. Pörtner, D.C. Roberts, M. Tignor, E.S. Poloczanska, K. Mintenbeck, A. Alegría, M. Craig, S. Langsdorf, S. Löschke, V. Möller, A. Okem, B. Rama (eds.)]. Cambridge University Press. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK and New York, NY, USA, 3056 pp., doi:10.1017/9781009325844.
- [2] Benestad, R.E. (2018) Implications of a decrease in the precipitation area for the past and the future, ERL, vol. 13, No.4, ERL-104904.R1, doi: 10.1088/1748-9326/aab375
- [3] Benestad, R.E., Lussana C., Lutz J., Dobler A. Landgren O.A., Haugen, J.E. Mezghani A., Casati B. Parding K.M. (2022) Global hydro-climatological indicators and changes in the global hydrological cycle and rainfall patterns, PLOS Climate, PCLM-D-21-00079R1, doi: 10.1371/journal.pclm.0000029
- [4] Simpson, J., Adler, R.F. and North, G.R. (1988) A proposed tropical rainfall measuring mission (TRMM) satellite, Bulletin of the American meteorological Society, 69(3), pp.278-295, doi: 10.1175/1520-0477(1988)069<0278:APTRMM>2.0.CO;2
- [5] Hersbach, H., Bell, B., Berrisford, P., Hirahara, S., Horanyi, A., Muñoz-Sabater, J., Nicolas, J., Peubey, C., Radu, R., Schepers, D., Simmons, A., Soci, C., Abdalla, S., Abellan, X., Balsamo, G., Bechtold, P., Biavati, G., Bidlot, J., Bonavita, M., Chiara, G., Dahlgren, P., Dee, D., Diamantakis, M., Dragani, R., Flemming, J., Forbes, R., Fuentes, M., Geer, A., Haimberger, L., Healy, S., Hogan, R.J., Holm, E., Janiskova, M., Keeley, S., Laloyaux, P., Lopez, P., Lupu, C., Radnoti, G., Rosnay, P., Rozum, I., Vamborg, F., Villaume, S., Thepaut, J. (2020) The ERA5 global reanalysis, Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society 146(730), 1999–2049, doi: 10.1002/qj.3803
- [6] Eyring, V., Bony, S., Meehl, G. A., Senior, C. A., Stevens, B., Stouffer, R. J., and Taylor, K. E. (2016) Overview of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6) experimental design and organization, Geosci. Model Dev., 9, 1937–1958, doi: 10.5194/gmd-9-1937-2016
- [7] Riahi, K., Van Vuuren, D.P., Kriegler, E., Edmonds, J., O'Neill, B.C., Fujimori, S., Bauer, N., Calvin, K., Dellink, R., Fricko, O. and Lutz, W. (2017) The Shared Socioeconomic Pathways and their energy, land use, and greenhouse gas emissions implications: An overview, Global environmental change, 42, pp.153-168, doi: 10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2016.05.009
- [8] Vinogradova N, Lee T, Boutin J, Drushka K, Fournier S, Sabia R, Stammer D, Bayler E, Reul N, Gordon A, Melnichenko O, Li L, Hackert E, Martin M, Kolodziejczyk N, Hasson A, Brown S, Misra S and Lindstrom E (2019) Satellite Salinity Observing System: Recent Discoveries and the Way Forward, Front. Mar. Sci. 6:243, doi: 10.3389/fmars.2019.00243